

ANALYSIS OF CRIMINAL ACTS AGAINST MINORS: A STUDY OF THE CASE OF THE MURDER OF A USTAZAH IN LAKE RANGAS

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Abstract

This study examines juvenile crime through a case study of the murder of a female Islamic teacher in Danau Rangas, Palangka Raya. A qualitative approach was used to examine the factors contributing to the thirteen-year-old perpetrator's behavior, including emotional distress, environmental influences, and poor communication within Islamic boarding schools. The results indicate that feelings of revenge and exposure to digital violence contribute to the child's aggressive behavior. Furthermore, the implementation of Law Number 11 of 2012 concerning the Juvenile Criminal Justice System demonstrates how the principle of restorative justice is implemented through social assistance, cross-agency coordination, and avoidance of detention. This study emphasizes that a legal approach to children needs to be balanced with attention to their psychological and social well-being for the effective development process.

Keywords: *Crime, Children, Child Criminalization*

INTRODUCTION

Child or adolescent crime is an unlawful act committed by individuals still in their moral and social developmental stage, where they lack emotional maturity and the ability to think rationally in assessing the consequences of their actions. This phenomenon arises from various factors, both internal and external, such as psychological conditions, family environment, social pressure, and peer influence. Children who grow up in families with poor communication patterns, minimal attention, or without adequate moral guidance are at greater risk of falling into deviant behavior. In a social context, juvenile crime not only disrupts public order but also indicates a weak system of moral development within the family and community. Child or adolescent crime does not emerge spontaneously, but is triggered by a combination of internal and external factors that influence their moral and social development. According to research by Deviana et al. (2024) in *Keraton: Journal of History, Education, and Culture*, internal factors originate within the child, such as psychological conditions, low self-control, and weak moral education from parents. Meanwhile, external factors include the influence of a disharmonious family environment, negative peer groups, a harsh social environment, and limited access to adequate education. When children live in conflict-ridden or neglectful families, and are exposed to environments prone to violence, they are more likely to develop deviant behavior. Furthermore, social and economic pressures, as well as exposure to media that normalizes violence, also strengthen children's tendency to commit crimes.

Data from the National Police Criminal Investigation Agency (Pusiknas Bareskrim Polri) shows that from January to July 10, 2024, there were 8,351 children named as suspects in 214,981 criminal cases across Indonesia. This figure reflects a quite alarming trend, with an average of over a thousand children involved in criminal acts each month. The peak of cases occurred in May with 1,481 child suspects, while the lowest period was recorded in early July with 408 children. Of all regional police (Polda) regions, North Sumatra recorded the highest number of children in conflict with the law, with 1,046, followed by East Java (841 children), South Sulawesi (621 children), and Metro Jaya (480 children). On the other hand, the North Kalimantan Regional Police recorded the lowest number of child suspects with only 17 cases. This trend demonstrates the need for a balanced social, educational, and legal approach to address the rampant involvement of children in crime in Indonesia. Data from the National Police Criminal Investigation Agency (Pusiknas Bareskrim Polri) also shows that by mid-2024, the number of children in conflict with the law had reached a significant level, with various legal statuses. A total of 8,351 children were registered as reported, suspects, or perpetrators of crimes, while 19,790 children were victims and

11,938 children were witnesses in various cases. Based on gender, boys dominated the number, accounting for 64.2 percent, while girls accounted for 35.8 percent. This difference indicates that boys are still more involved in legal cases, both as perpetrators and victims. According to data from the National Crime Information Center (Pusiknas) of the Indonesian National Police Criminal Investigation Agency (Bareskrim Polri), the number of children involved in crime in Indonesia continues to increase year after year. Each month, more than a thousand children are recorded as suspects, and by May 2024, the number had reached 1,481. Data from the Correctional Database System shows that as of July 12, 2024, there were 2,153 children with criminal suspect status. Meanwhile, data from the Directorate General of Corrections at the Ministry of Law and Human Rights recorded that the number of child suspects in August 2023 was 1,475, a decrease from 1,530 in 2022, but still higher than 1,365 in 2021. This trend illustrates that despite annual fluctuations, the level of child involvement in crime remains at a concerning level. This situation indicates challenges in the moral and social development of the younger generation, especially amid changing values and increasingly complex environmental influences.

Worse, criminal cases involving minors also occurred in Central Kalimantan. In 2024, a murder case occurred in Rangas Lake, Palangka Raya, starting on the night of May 14, 2024 when a student with the initials FA (13) stabbed his teacher, a female Islamic teacher named STN (35), in the Islamic boarding school environment where they lived. Based on the results of the Palangka Raya Police investigation, the act was motivated by the perpetrator's feeling of revenge because he had received punishment from the victim for disciplinary violations at the Islamic boarding school. Before the incident, the perpetrator was given a sanction to copy two chapters of the Quran after previously being sun-dried as a form of guidance. At around 11:00 PM WIB, FA woke up from his sleep, went to the ustazah's house through an unlocked window, then took a kitchen knife and stabbed the victim's head and chest nine times. The victim, who had screamed for help, was found covered in blood and was immediately taken to Betang Pabelum Hospital, but his life could not be saved due to severe bleeding. Based on the consideration of the perpetrator's age, who was still under 14 years old, the police did not detain him, but handed over the assistance process to the Correctional Center (Bapas) and the Social Service in accordance with the provisions of Law Number 11 of 2012 concerning the Juvenile Criminal Justice System.

After the murder of Ustazah STN (35) at the Islamic boarding school on Jalan Danau Rangas, Palangka Raya City on May 14, 2024, the investigation continued until the end of June 2024. Based on the statement of the Head of Criminal Investigation Unit of the Palangka Raya Police, Commissioner Ronny M. Nababan, the perpetrator FA (13) still had mandatory reporting status because the case file had not been declared complete by the Palangka Raya District Attorney. From the results of the investigation, the motive for the murder was confirmed to be triggered by pent-up revenge due to the sanctions previously given to the victim. In December 2023, the perpetrator was sentenced to sunbathing for committing a violation, and on May 13, 2024, was again given the sanction of copying two juz of the Qur'an after leaving the Islamic boarding school without permission. The day after carrying out the punishment, the perpetrator recalled his annoyance and carried out an attack with a knife which caused the victim to die from wounds to the face, neck, chest and arms. The evidence has been secured, and the victim was buried on May 16, 2024 at the Islamic TPU Jalan Tjilik Riwut KM 12, Palangka Raya, while the legal process is still awaiting complete administrative documents from the prosecutor's office.

As a follow-up to the investigation process, the Palangka Raya Police held a reconstruction of the murder of a female Islamic teacher at the Hidayatullah Islamic Boarding School, Jalan Danau Rangas, Bukit Tunggal Village, Jekan Raya District, on Friday, August 9, 2024. This reconstruction was carried out to clarify the chronology of events and ensure the perpetrator's statement matches the facts on the ground. The activity began with a troop roll call as a form of checking the readiness of personnel on duty in security. Head of Operations of the Palangka Raya Police, Commissioner Ganda B. Napitupulu, explained that all officers involved were asked to adhere to Standard Operating Procedures (SOPs) throughout the process to avoid violations during the reconstruction stage. In fact, the criminal behavior of children as occurred in Rangas Lake cannot be considered trivial. This is because such behavior has resulted in the loss of a person's life. However, Law Number 11 of 2012 concerning the Juvenile Criminal Justice System does not allow law enforcement to impose sanctions on minors, as sanctions are enforced in other cases of loss of life. Law Number 11 of 2012 concerning the Juvenile Criminal Justice System regulates the procedures for handling criminal cases involving children, with an emphasis on protecting children's rights and implementing restorative justice. This regulation replaces Law Number 3 of 1997 concerning Juvenile Courts, which was deemed to have not met the legal needs of society. This law explains that children in conflict with the law include child perpetrators, victims, and witnesses of criminal acts.

Its basic principles include humane, non-discriminatory treatment, respect for the child's views, and the application of criminal penalties and detention only as a last resort. In practice, this system prioritizes diversion, namely the transfer of juvenile cases from the criminal justice process to an out-of-court process, involving the perpetrator, victim, family, and community to reach a fair agreement. Furthermore, this law regulates children's rights at all stages of the legal process, including legal assistance, identity protection, education, and rehabilitation. The ultimate goal is to ensure that the legal process for children is not merely punitive, but also fosters and reintegrates children into their social environment.

The purpose of this study is to understand in depth the causes behind the involvement of minors in the crime of murder in Danau Rangas, as well as to analyze how the law enforcement process and the application of the principle of restorative justice are applied to the perpetrators in accordance with the provisions of Law Number 11 of 2012 concerning the Juvenile Criminal Justice System. Through a qualitative approach, this study seeks to explore the social experiences, psychological conditions, and environmental influences that shape the perpetrators' behavior, while also examining how law enforcement officers balance aspects of justice and protection of children's rights in handling the case. This research is interesting to conduct because the murder case in Danau Rangas not only reflects a form of crime committed by young children, but also shows real challenges in the Indonesian legal system in handling serious crimes committed by children.

METHOD

This research uses a qualitative method with a case study approach to examine in-depth juvenile crime in the murder case of a female Islamic teacher in Danau Rangas. Data were collected through interviews with the police and other relevant parties, as well as through a review of investigative documents and media reports. This approach was chosen to understand the causal factors, psychological conditions, and environmental influences on the perpetrator's behavior, while also assessing the law enforcement process implemented in accordance with the provisions of the Juvenile Criminal Justice System. The data obtained were then analyzed descriptively by connecting field findings with criminological theory and the concept of juvenile delinquency.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Criminology Theory and the Concept of Juvenile Delinquency

Criminology is a branch of science that studies crime from various perspectives, including its causes, perpetrators, and societal reactions. Etymologically, the term "criminology" comes from the words "crime," meaning crime, and "logos," meaning knowledge. This term was first introduced by Paul Topinard (1830–1911), a French anthropologist. According to Wolfgang, Savitz, and Johnston in *The Sociology of Crime and Delinquency*, criminology encompasses the body of scientific knowledge and understanding of the phenomena of crime obtained through the analysis of emerging information, patterns, and uniformities, including the study of causal factors, characteristics of criminals, and societal responses to these crimes.

In addition, Frank P. William and Marilyn ScShane classify various criminological theories into 3 (three) parts, namely:

1. Classical Theory and Positivist Theory

Classical theory focuses on legal statutes, government structures, and human rights, while Positivist theory focuses on pathology in criminal behavior, prevention, and improvement of criminal behavior of individuals;

2. Structural and Process Theory

Structural theory is more based on the way society is organized and its effect on behavior. This theory is also called Strain Theories because of their assumption that a disorganized society creates strain which leads to deviant behavior. The assumption is that society creates strain or tension that can lead to deviant behavior, while Process Theories explain how someone becomes a criminal.

3. Consensus Theory and Conflict Theory

Consensus Theory is based on the assumption that there is a consensus within society, whereby some individuals agree with the rest of society. Therefore, there are generally accepted values within society. In contrast to consensus theory, Conflict Theory assumes that there is little agreement within society and that people hold conflicting values.

In other sources, criminology is defined as a scientific discipline that studies various aspects of perpetrators and criminal acts, including the patterns or methods used by perpetrators in committing their acts. This science seeks to deeply understand the factors behind the emergence of crime and to find the most effective

strategies to prevent and overcome criminal acts in society. E.H. Sutherland views criminology as a field of knowledge that examines crime as a social phenomenon. This study includes the process of forming laws, violations of these laws, and various forms of societal reactions to violations of the law. According to Sutherland, the scope of criminology is divided into three main branches, namely:

1. Sociology of Law

From this perspective, crime is understood as an act prohibited by law and subject to sanctions if committed. Therefore, it is the law that determines whether an act is classified as a crime. Studies in this branch focus on analyzing the causes of crime and the factors influencing legal development, particularly criminal law.

2. Etiology of Crime

This branch focuses on efforts to discover the causes of crime. In criminology, the study of the etiology of crime is considered the most fundamental because it serves to explain the roots of criminal behavior from various social and individual perspectives.

3. Penology

This discipline focuses on the science of punishment, encompassing not only the forms and implementation of punishment but also repressive and preventive crime control efforts. Sutherland includes aspects of rights and policies related to crime prevention within the scope of penology.

Juvenile delinquency is a form of behavior that indicates social disruption in adolescents due to a lack of attention and support from their social environment, thus encouraging the emergence of actions that deviate from societal norms. However, violations of norms committed by adolescents cannot be directly categorized as crimes, because such a label is considered excessive considering that adolescents are legally still classified as children. Based on Law Number 23 of 2002, a child is an individual under the age of 18, so handling cases of juvenile delinquency is carried out with a different approach than handling crimes committed by adults. Etymologically, the term juvenile delinquency comes from the word juvenile, meaning child or adolescent, and delinquency, meaning an offense committed by a child or adolescent. Therefore, this term can be literally interpreted as a violation or deviant act committed by a child. When linked to the perpetrator, juvenile delinquency refers to deviant behavior or unlawful acts committed by children or adolescents, often referred to as delinquents. According to Dryfoos, juvenile delinquency encompasses a wide range of behaviors, from actions deemed inappropriate to social norms, such as frequent truancy, to status violations like running away from home, to actions that are considered criminal, such as theft. Kartono, meanwhile, lists several factors influencing juvenile delinquency as follows:

1. Internal Factors

1) Negative Frustration Reactions

1. Aggression is a very basic form of emotional reaction, characterized by strong outbursts of anger, aggressive actions, and uncontrollable, violent or sadistic behavior. These emotional outbursts can disrupt a child's thinking ability and personality stability, leading to chaos within themselves and their environment. This condition can then escalate into fights, acts of violence, terrorizing others, and various other aggressive behaviors.
2. Regression is an emotional reaction that is childish and appears regardless of age, which can hinder a child's ability to adapt to their surroundings;
3. Fixation is a condition where a person is tied to a rigid and unnatural pattern of behavior, for example acting as he pleases, being rude, holding grudges, or showing hostility;
4. Rationalization is an attempt to defend oneself by changing actions that are actually unreasonable to appear acceptable, and tends to blame others for one's failures and shortcomings in order to maintain self-esteem.
5. Justification is a way for someone to justify their own actions or attitudes with inappropriate and uncontrolled reasons;
6. Projection is the habit of throwing out one's thoughts, feelings, mistakes or bad desires onto other people so that they are not seen as one's own weaknesses;
7. The sour grape technique is a self-defense mechanism that involves lowering the value of something that is actually very desirable, simply because it cannot be achieved;
8. The sweet orange technique is an attempt to cover up one's shortcomings, mistakes or failures by giving an excessively positive assessment in order to remain comfortable and satisfied with the situation;
9. Identification is the process of identifying oneself with another party to cover up feelings of inadequacy, so that teenagers try to imitate certain figures in order to be accepted by their environment;

10. Narcissism is the view that oneself is the most superior, powerful, and most valuable, which causes teenagers to have difficulty accepting criticism, are easily provoked, and tend to act as they please;
11. Autism is the tendency to withdraw from the surrounding environment and feel that only oneself is right, so that teenagers close themselves off from the influence and views of others.

2) Observation and Response Disorders

Disturbances in the reaction and perception processes can manifest as illusions, hallucinations, or false images. In these conditions, the child's responses no longer correspond to the reality around them, but are instead influenced by inappropriate mental processing, leading to misperceptions. As a result, the child may exhibit irritable behavior, become aggressive, and even engage in arguments or violence.

3) Thinking and Intelligence Disorders

Thinking skills play a significant role in helping individuals adapt appropriately to their environment, as healthy individuals are able to correct errors through logical thinking and distinguish between fantasy and reality. Conversely, in children with impaired thinking skills, erroneous mental processes are used to maintain views that are not in line with reality, resulting in erroneous responses and behaviors that tend to be aggressive and difficult to control. Parents and educators have a significant influence on the development of children's thinking skills, which can be hampered by treatment such as unfair punishment, unreasonable prohibitions, or other repressive actions; however, they can develop well if children are given space to express their opinions, learn to solve problems, and have the opportunity to play a more active role in everyday life.

4) Emotional Disorders

Feelings are closely related to the fulfillment of human hopes, desires, and needs, and play a crucial role in understanding the meaning of life. Therefore, respecting others' feelings also means respecting their needs and desires. When mood disorders occur, they can manifest in various forms, such as an inability to control emotions, unstable mood swings, a lack of empathy, emotional overload, fear, anxiety, and feelings of low self-esteem.

2. External Factors

1) Family Factors

The family is the primary environment that shapes a child's character and personality through socialization, love, guidance, and attention. A family environment that is not harmonious or lacking in support, discipline, and affection can impact a child's mental development and potentially trigger juvenile delinquency.

2) School Factors

Unfavorable school environments include building schools that do not meet requirements, activities that take a long time at school, irregular curriculum changes, teachers who are not liked, and strict rules make teenagers bored, annoyed and apathetic. As a result, children are involved in disobeying all the rules, they want to be wild, they want to talk, they become aggressive, and they also like to fight to release frustration and resentment; Milieu (Environmental Factors);

3) School Factors

The surrounding environment does not always have a positive influence on a child's education and development, as it can contain individuals from diverse backgrounds, including troubled adolescents, criminals, and groups that reject social norms. These conditions can trigger negative emotional reactions in adolescents who are still unstable, making them more susceptible to imitating criminal, immoral, or antisocial behavior. Exposure to immoral and violent adult viewing, reading, or behavior can also encourage them to imitate and adopt deviant behavior.

In relation to this research, Criminology studies crime as a social phenomenon, including perpetrators, causes, and societal reactions to violations of the law. In the context of minors, deviant behavior or juvenile delinquency is understood as a form of violation that arises from the inability of adolescents to adapt to their environment. Internal factors such as unstable emotions and erroneous mindsets, as well as external factors such as lack of family attention, non-conducive schools, and negative social environments can trigger the emergence of antisocial acts. This understanding is the basis for analyzing cases of Criminality of Minors (Study on the Murder Case of Ustazah in Rangas Lake) so that the handling approach is different from that of adult perpetrators and places more emphasis on guidance and prevention efforts.

Causes of Juvenile Crime (A Study of the Murder Case of a Muslim Teacher in Rangas Lake)

The phenomenon of crime involving minors is a complex social issue because it concerns not only legal aspects but also closely related to the psychological development and social environment of the child. In the murder case of a female Islamic teacher in Danau Rangas, Palangka Raya City, the 13-year-old perpetrator exhibited symptoms of behavioral deviation arising from the interaction of emotional pressure, environmental influences, and weak self-control. Based on the results of the investigation described in the study, the child acted out of revenge after receiving disciplinary sanctions from his teacher. This pattern indicates a breakdown in communication between educators and students, where guidance actions are interpreted as a form of punishment that fosters hatred. Such a situation reflects the child's lack of ability to manage emotions and understand the moral consequences of his actions.

From an interview with Nur Kholifah Yuli Astuti (37 years old), a member of the Indonesian National Police who served in Subunit 1 PPA Polresta Palangka Raya, it was revealed that the perpetrator's social background played a major role in the formation of deviant behavior. She said, "the factors come from the environment, games, and then a lot of pressure on this child from his friends." This statement shows that external influences, such as socializing and the habit of playing violent games like PUBG, contribute to the formation of children's perceptions of violence as something normal. Children who are frequently exposed to violent content tend to imitate these behavioral patterns without considering the moral values that should be controlling their actions.

One of the main causes of the violence in this case was a feeling of resentment that grew from the experience of punishment from his teacher. Based on interviews and investigative statements, the perpetrator's child had been subjected to disciplinary action by the victim's teacher for violating Islamic boarding school rules. The punishment consisted of imprisonment and the obligation to copy two chapters of the Quran as a form of moral development. However, for a child who was only around thirteen years old and emotionally immature, the punishment was perceived as a form of humiliation and injustice. Feelings of shame and offense then turned into suppressed anger, which ultimately developed into a drive for revenge. This resentment did not arise spontaneously, but rather accumulated from unresolved hurt.

Furthermore, the family environment is also a crucial source of behavioral influence. Many children grow up without adequate emotional and moral guidance from their parents, seeking validation outside the home. In this case, social pressure and feelings of disrespect within the Islamic boarding school environment exacerbate the child's aggressive impulses. Previous research has shown that children who experience verbal abuse, rejection, or physical punishment in the educational environment are at higher risk of developing antisocial behavior. The combination of feelings of offense, wounded self-esteem, and the urge to retaliate are key triggers for extreme acts such as murder. This is evident in the fact that the perpetrator committed the attack after recalling the punishment given the day before, indicating a built-up resentment.

The source's statement also emphasized that children's psychological well-being presents a unique challenge during the investigation. Nur Kholifah stated, "It's quite difficult to understand or predict the psychological well-being of these children, as some are easy to talk to, while others are difficult." This statement demonstrates that emotional instability in children can be a barrier to understanding and processing traumatic events. In this context, criminal behavior is not simply a violation of the law, but a manifestation of unresolved internal conflict. This situation is exacerbated by the lack of psychological support in educational settings, preventing children from having a safe space to express their negative feelings constructively.

Modern technology and digital culture also shape the character of today's children. Easy access to violent content, both through online games and social media, distorts perceptions of power and courage. The children involved in the Rangas Lake case are believed to have frequently played war games, which indirectly normalizes aggressive behavior. According to Bandura's social learning theory, aggressive behavior can emerge through the process of imitation of repeated visual stimuli. In other words, the more frequently a child watches or plays games with violent themes, the higher the likelihood that they will practice such behavior in real life, especially when combined with unresolved emotional stress. In addition to media influence, peer pressure also plays a significant role. The interviewee explained that "pressure, such as bullying by peers, should not be allowed to happen and is not justified." This kind of social pressure can create feelings of inferiority and helplessness in children, which then drives them to seek extreme means to assert their existence. In certain situations, resentment and the desire to gain control over their environment can be powerful motivations for committing illegal acts. Thus, peer group dynamics are not only a space for socialization, but also a potential arena for fostering aggressive behavior if not adequately

monitored. Meanwhile, from a family and educational perspective, weak moral supervision and a harsh disciplinary approach can worsen a child's psychological well-being. Punishments such as sunbathing or being required to copy two chapters of the Quran may be intended to educate, but for emotionally unstable children, they can be interpreted as insults or injustice. Without warm and empathetic communication, children easily interpret punishment as a form of hatred from adults, rather than a learning experience. This pattern demonstrates a disparity between the intention of education and the child's psychological acceptance.

The Law Enforcement Process for Minor Criminals (A Study of the Murder Case of a Ustazah in Rangas Lake) Based on Law Number 11 of 2012 Concerning the Juvenile Criminal Justice System

The law enforcement process against the perpetrator of the murder of a thirteen-year-old female Islamic teacher in Danau Rangas was carried out in accordance with Law Number 11 of 2012 concerning the Juvenile Criminal Justice System (SPPA). Based on an interview with Nur Kholifah Yuli Astuti (37 years old), a member of the Indonesian National Police from Subunit 1 PPA of the Palangka Raya Police, the police from the beginning of handling the case have treated the perpetrator as a child in conflict with the law, not as an adult criminal. She explained that the case was handled while still guaranteeing children's rights and prioritizing the principle of non-discrimination. The process began with the receipt of a report by the Islamic boarding school in the early hours of May 15, 2024, at around 2:30 a.m., followed by an initial examination of witnesses and the perpetrator. During this stage, the authorities were careful not to take any action that could cause psychological stress on the child, considering his very young age and vulnerability to trauma.

In the interview, Nur Kholifah emphasized that from the outset, the police had not detained the perpetrator. She stated that "if the perpetrator is a child, there must be assistance from the social services, and the child's father will provide assistance," and added that "the detention stage is actually a last resort. As long as there is still a guarantor in accordance with Article 32 of the Juvenile Criminal Justice System Law, then we will prefer another route" (Interview, 2024). This statement illustrates the application of the basic principle of the Child Protection and Juvenile Detention System (SPPA), namely that detention of children may only be carried out as a last resort and for the shortest possible time. In this case, because the perpetrator still has parents who are willing to act as guarantors, he was not placed in detention but was required to undergo regular mandatory reporting to the police station. This measure is intended to ensure that the child remains under legal supervision without depriving him of his right to be in a family environment.

Counseling is a crucial aspect of the entire investigation process in this case. According to sources, each stage of the investigation involves the Correctional Center (Bapas) and the Social Services Department. They are present to ensure that the perpetrator receives humane treatment and emotional protection during the legal process. The presence of counseling officers serves not only an administrative function but also a balancing act between legal and psychological aspects. Children experiencing emotional distress due to the investigation process can more easily calm down when accompanied by someone who understands their psychological condition. This approach aligns with the mandate of Articles 23 and 24 of Law No. 11 of 2012, which mandates social and legal counseling for children in conflict with the law to ensure that the judicial process continues to prioritize the child's best interests.

The investigative procedures applied also differ from those for adult perpetrators. Nur Kholifah explained, "While child perpetrators are accompanied by officers, adults are not provided with any assistance other than legal counsel" (Interview, 2024). This means children are treated with greater care during interrogations and examinations. The officers involved are required to adapt their communication methods to avoid causing undue fear or pressure. In practice, children are not permitted to be coerced into providing information, and the entire process must be conducted in a child-friendly environment. In fact, according to the interviewee, the police ensure that children feel safe throughout the process. This aligns with the principles of restorative justice at the heart of the SPPA, where the approach is not solely punitive but also fosters and restores social relationships between the perpetrator, victim, and community.

In addition to legal assistance, cross-agency coordination is also a crucial part of law enforcement for children. The resource person stated that "the KPAI (Indonesian Child Protection Commission) doesn't actually exist here, but there is the City's UPT PPA (Education and Child Protection Unit) and the Child Protection Agency (Bapas), with an MoU in place, so child perpetrators are certainly assisted by them." This collaboration between the police, child protection agencies, and social agencies ensures that every decision taken takes into account the child's welfare. For example, when preparing the investigation report, Bapas officers consider the child's psychological condition and recommend appropriate forms of guidance. This system helps create a balance

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between legal demands and rehabilitation needs, preventing children from repeating similar actions in the future. The law enforcement process in the murder case of the female Islamic teacher in Danau Rangas demonstrates the concrete application of the principles of restorative justice as stipulated in Law Number 11 of 2012 concerning the Child Protection System (SPPA). The police strive not only to enforce the law but also to protect children's rights by not detaining them, providing social and legal assistance, and establishing cross-agency cooperation. In an interview, Nur Kholifah explained that the child perpetrator is still required to report regularly while awaiting the completion of the files from the prosecutor's office. This demonstrates that the juvenile criminal justice system is not only oriented towards punishment, but also towards development and rehabilitation. This case illustrates how the law can be implemented while upholding humanitarian values, ensuring that children do not lose the opportunity to return to their social environment with a more mature moral understanding.

In simple terms, the process of handling this case is as follows;

Case Reporting	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - The Islamic boarding school reported the incident to the Palangka Raya Police on the morning of May 15, 2024. - Police received the report at 02:30 WIB and immediately went to the scene.
Preliminary Investigation	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Police conducted examinations of witnesses and child perpetrators using a child-friendly approach. - The perpetrator was identified as a 13-year-old child and was processed according to juvenile criminal procedures.
Help for Children	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Since the initial stages of the investigation, the child has been accompanied by the Social Services and Correctional Center (Bapas). - This assistance ensures humane treatment and psychological protection for children during the legal process.
No Detention Policy	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Based on Article 32 of Law no. 11 of 2012, detaining children is considered the last step. - Because the child still has parents acting as guarantors, detention is not applied. - The child is required to report regularly to the police station.
Inter-Agency Coordination	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Coordination involves the Palangka Raya Police, Bapas, and the UPT PPA of Palangka Raya City based on the established MoU. - Bapas provides psychological assessments and rehabilitation recommendations during the legal process.
Implementation of Restorative Justice Principles	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - The legal process is focused not on punishment, but on the recovery and rehabilitation of children. - The child still has the right to legal aid, education and social rehabilitation. - Police ensure that social relations between children and society can be restored.
Mandatory Reporting and Submission of Case Files to the Prosecutor's Office	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Child perpetrators are required to report periodically while waiting for the completion of case files by the Prosecutor's Office. - The entire process is carried out with the best interests of the child and humanitarian values in mind.

CONCLUSION

The phenomenon of juvenile crime, as illustrated by the murder of a female Islamic teacher in Danau Rangas, demonstrates that violent behavior in children results from a complex interaction between psychological, social, and environmental factors. The growing sense of revenge stemming from disciplinary experiences at Islamic boarding schools demonstrates how a child's inability to manage emotions can lead to extreme actions. Furthermore, the lack of empathetic communication between educators and students, along with the influence of a digital environment that normalizes violence, reinforces children's tendency to react impulsively. This situation indicates that character development in children needs to be carried out comprehensively through emotional, educational, and social approaches so that children can understand the moral consequences of their actions.

From a legal perspective, the application of Law No. 11 of 2012 concerning the Juvenile Criminal Justice System in this case demonstrates that law enforcement can be carried out in harmony with the principles of child protection. The police and related institutions successfully implemented a restorative justice-oriented investigation process by providing social assistance and avoiding detention. This approach creates space for the child's psychological and social rehabilitation without neglecting legal responsibility. Therefore, handling cases of children in conflict with the law is not only an effort to uphold justice but also a means of reshaping the child's character so that they can adapt healthily in society.

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ANALYSIS OF CRIMINAL ACTS AGAINST MINORS: A STUDY OF THE CASE OF THE MURDER OF A USTAZAH IN LAKE RANGAS

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